

Examining the Role of Attitudes towards Ageing in Predicting Well-being and Life Satisfaction among Elderly Women

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Attitudes towards ageing include the opinions, views, stereotypes and mindsets an individual has toward the process of ageing. Research shows that negative attitudes are more prevalent than positive ones and can strongly influence life experiences. Older women may be particularly vulnerable due to the cumulative social experiences they have faced across the lifespan. In addition to age-related stereotypes, women often encounter gender-based discrimination, and in later life these forms of bias can intersect. Therefore, attitudes may have significant impact on multiple areas of older women's lives. The current study seeks to explore how attitudes towards ageing can influence well-being and life satisfaction among older women. A sample of 50 female participants, between the ages of 65 and 80 years (Mean = 72.82), participated in this study, whose scores on Attitude to Ageing Questionnaire (Laidlaw et al., 2007), the PERMA Profiler (Butler & Kern, 2016), and Satisfaction with Life Scale (Diener et al., 1985) were obtained. The data has been analysed using correlation and regression analyses. Positive perception of physical change and psychological growth were positively and significantly correlated with facets of well-being (range of $r = .286 - .417$), but the association between psychosocial loss and well-being was not found to be significant among this sample. Positive perception of physical change significantly predicted well-being among older women. This research highlights the interaction between attitudes, well-being, and life satisfaction among older adult women. This study has a wide range of implications for older adults and health professionals for the geriatric population.

Keywords: Attitudes to ageing, life satisfaction, well-being, PERMA model

Background

Need of the Study

The United Nations and the World Health Organization (2019) have reported that the global population is experiencing a positive shift in average life expectancy, reflecting significant advancement in healthcare, nutrition and overall living standards. While this demographic transition represents major achievements, it also carries far-reaching social, economic and psychological implications. For older adults, increased longevity can frequently accompany a range of challenges such as decline in physical health, reduced functional capacity, social isolation and heightened vulnerability to mental health concerns (WHO, 2025; Beard et al., 2016). Beyond these challenges, a particularly critical, yet overlooked issue lies in an individual's perception of ageing. Research suggests that negative self-perceptions of ageing are associated with poorer health outcomes, reduced life satisfaction and even increased mortality risk (Levy, 2009; Wurm et al., 2017). Subsequently, although improvements in healthcare systems and living conditions may enhance the external circumstances of later life, the overall quality of life among older adults cannot be fully

realised without fostering positive attitudes and adaptive psychological orientations towards ageing (Stephoe et al., 2015; Levy et al., 2018). Despite growing evidence on the importance of ageing attitudes, limited research has specifically examined how these perceptions influence psychological well-being and life satisfaction among older women, a group that may experience unique age- and gender-related challenges. Understanding this relationship is essential for developing targeted interventions and policies aimed at promoting healthier and more fulfilling ageing experiences among elderly women.

Attitudes towards Ageing

Ageing-related attitudes can play a significant and potentially deterministic role in shaping the lives and lived experiences of older adults. Attitudes about ageing refer to the emotional, cognitive and evaluative responses towards older adults as a group as well as towards one's own ageing experience, reflecting individual and societal perceptions (Hess, 2006). Attitudes towards any concept or aspect of life can vary in nature, but it is unfortunate that negative attitudes about ageing have been reported to be more prevalent (Ng et al., 2015). Biological differences, personal experiences, expectations by the society and cultural norms can play an important role in determining the kind of attitudes held by an individual. Negative attitudes about ageing prevail not only among the older adults, but the society at large. These attitudes are often formed based on the experiences of older adults throughout their lives and the stereotypes that exist in collective mindset of the society (Levy et al., 2009).

Gender differences have been observed with respect to ageing related attitudes, emphasising the differences in societal beauty standards with respect to appearance, gender-based discrimination, social roles and responsibilities, retirement and financial security. Older females, may have predispositions towards negative attitudes

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toward ageing due to the experiences they have collectively faced as a group (Shakeri & North, 2025). There is a greater pressure on women to adhere to the societal beauty standards which become and additional worry when changes to physical appearance first become apparent (Lipowska, 2016). In contrast, older men may experience pressures related to maintaining perceptions of strength, productivity, independence, and financial stability, particularly after retirement, which can influence their attitudes toward ageing (Wurm et al., 2017). While both older males and females may face discrimination based on their age, older females often also face additional gender-based biases. Older men, however, may encounter challenges related to loss of occupational identity, reduced social networks after retirement, and cultural expectations surrounding emotional restraint, which may shape their experiences of ageing differently (Wurm et al., 2017). In some parts of the world, the older women play the role of the head of the family, but at the same time older women are more likely to be victims of elder abuse in the form of monetary exploitation, neglect, maltreatment in domestic settings, etc (Gurjar & Kumari, 2025). Similarly, older men may also be vulnerable to financial exploitation and neglect, though such experiences are often underreported due to stigma and societal expectations about masculinity (Hines, 2015; Mouton et al., 2002).

The kind of attitude an individual has can have significant impact on their experiences during old age. Having a positive attitude, as opposed to a negative attitude, about ageing has been linked with quality of life (Top & Dikmetaş, 2015), health benefits for both physical and mental health, and also an inclination towards engaging in health promoting behaviours (Brown et al., 2015). A positive perspective also fosters hope and resilience among older adults when they face challenges and stresses of old age and life in general (Dang & Zhang, 2022; Lima et al., 2023; Kunuroglu & Yuzbasi, 2021). A series of studies conducted by Levy (2002) suggests that positive attitudes about ageing are linked to longevity, and individuals having a positive outlook live on average 7.5 years longer than those who have a negative view.

In light of the evidence, ageing-related attitudes emerge as a critical psychosocial factor influencing multiple domains of later life, particularly for older women who may face intersecting age- and gender-based challenges. Such attitudes can shape how individuals perceive their health, engage in social roles, respond to stressors, and evaluate their overall quality of life. Importantly, ageing-related attitudes may significantly influence key psychological outcomes, including well-being and life satisfaction, by affecting emotional experiences, resilience, sense of purpose, and personal fulfilment in older adulthood. While negative societal stereotypes remain pervasive, research underscores the protective value of positive ageing attitudes in fostering healthier, more adaptive ageing trajectories. Against this backdrop, the present study specifically focuses on the association of ageing-related attitudes with well-being and life satisfaction among elderly women, with the aim of better understanding the role of perceptions of ageing in shaping their overall quality of life.

Well-being and Ageing

Well-being is the overall physical, mental, emotional, and social state of an individual. Seligman (2011) proposed the PERMA model of well-being, which defines well-being as a combination of five elements: Positive Emotion (P), Engagement (E), Relationships (R), Meaning (M) and Accomplishment (A). The element of positive emotions includes experiencing emotions like happiness, joy, awe, pride, love and other positive feelings. These feelings help one

remain optimistic, constructive and resilient in face of challenges. The element of engagement has often been compared to the concept of 'flow' given by Csikszentmihalyi (1992). It includes being fully absorbed and immersed in the activities that hold meaning and value for the individual. One is engaged when they lose track of time, or feel a sense of clarity regarding the task at hand, or when one feels the most efficient and productive and can have fun. Seligman (2011) also emphasized the importance of having positive and healthy relationships. Having fulfilling relationships with family and friends provides one with a sense of belongingness and having people who can support them are crucial to one's well-being. The fourth essential element of this model is meaning, which includes having a sense of meaning and purpose in life. It includes the acceptance of something greater than just the self and contributing to the greater good, which helps a person feel like their life matters, has value and is worthwhile (Peterson, Park, & Seligman, 2005; Steger, 2012). Accomplishment is the last element of this model, which encompasses having goals, the drive to reach these goals and the sense of achievement after reaching them. Having goals can help a person feel a sense of direction in their life and enhance the opportunities for success and a sense of mastery. High levels of well-being are known as flourishing, which is achieved by cultivating these five elements in one's life (Seligman, 2011).

Well-being among older adults can be meaningfully understood through Seligman's PERMA model, which conceptualizes flourishing as comprising five core elements: Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment (Seligman, 2011). In later life, positive emotion may involve cultivating gratitude and emotional regulation; engagement can be experienced through hobbies, volunteering, or cognitively stimulating activities; relationships remain central as social connectedness is strongly associated with better mental and physical health outcomes; meaning may derive from spirituality, family roles, or community involvement; and accomplishment can include achieving personal goals or maintaining independence despite age-related changes (Waterworth et al., 2019). Research suggests that these PERMA components are positively associated with life satisfaction and psychological well-being across the lifespan, including older adulthood (Butler & Kern, 2016; Seligman, 2011) highlighting the model's relevance for understanding and promoting flourishing in later life.

Life Satisfaction and Ageing

Life satisfaction refers to an individual's assessment of their life circumstances and quality of life. It is a subjective measure of the degree to which one feels fulfilled, satisfied and perceives the presence of meaning in their life (Diener, 1984; Steger et al., 2006). "Life satisfaction is the degree to which a person positively evaluates the overall quality of his/her life as a whole. In other words, how much the person likes the life he/she leads" (Veenhoven, 1996).

According to the last stage of Erikson's (1950) theory, "integrity versus despair" is the stage where an individual reflects back on their own life and makes cognitive evaluations pertaining to the quality of their life and how satisfied and content they feel while looking back. One reaches this stage during late adulthood, which is around the age of 65 years. Integrity is understood as the feeling of fulfilment due to the belief that one's life has had a purpose and is meaningful. This stage involves overcoming the past and reaching a stage of being whole (Erikson, 1982). On the contrary, despair encompasses feelings of regret, disappointment and guilt over opportunities missed during life. Older adults during this stage make subjective

evaluations of how satisfied they feel about the kind of life they have lived and what lies ahead (Erikson, 1982). For older adults many factors contribute to life satisfaction, like their health status (Wang, 2002), well-being (Nakamura et al., 2022), level of resilience (Zheng, Huang, & Fu, 2020), nature of their relationships with others, autonomy (Li-Hsing & Chia-Chan, 2020), independence (Kudo et al., 2007), individual characteristics like their personality traits (Stephan, 2009), etc.

This study aims to examine the role of ageing-related attitudes in shaping psychological outcomes among older women. It seeks to explore the impact of ageing-related attitudes on well-being and life satisfaction in later life. The study intends to better understand how perceptions of ageing contribute to the subjective experiences of older women by focusing on these dimensions.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1a*: Psychological growth and positive perceptions of physical change are positively related with well-being.
- *H1b*: Psychosocial loss is negatively related with well-being.
- *H2a*: Psychological growth and positive perceptions of physical change are positively related with life satisfaction.
- *H2b*: Psychosocial loss is negatively related with life satisfaction.

Method

Participants

The sample for the current study comprised 50 older females between the ages of 65 and 80 years. The mean age was found to be 72.82 years ($SD = 4.6$). The participants belonged to Patiala city of Punjab, and included those women who reported an absence of major diseases, disabilities or recent trauma. Individuals from residential care facilities were excluded from this study. The participants responded to scales used to assess ageing related attitudes, well-being and life satisfaction.

Measures

The Attitudes to Ageing Questionnaire (AAQ; Laidlaw et al., 2007). The Attitudes to Ageing Questionnaire (AAQ) is a 24-item self-report measure of positive and negative attitudes to ageing. The questionnaire assesses three facets of ageing namely, Psychosocial Loss, Physical Change and Psychological Growth. Each of these facets is measured using an 8-item subscale. The subscales cover diverse features of the ageing process, the psychosocial loss subscale (negative attitudes) measures the losses that accompany the process of ageing, physical change (positive attitude) assesses one's attitude towards age related changes in physical functioning and the score on psychological growth (positive attitude) is an indicator of the personal growth associated with growing old. The questionnaire provides three scores for the three subscales, and positive attitude toward ageing can be inferred from higher scores on the physical change and psychological growth subscales and a lower score on the psychosocial loss subscale. The internal consistency for the subscales was satisfactory, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging between .85 and .89.

The PERMA-Profiler (Butler & Kern, 2016). The PERMA Profiler is a 23-item scale measuring well-being and its constituent elements. The scale is based on the PERMA Model (Seligman, 2011) and comprises of items for positive emotions, negative emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, accomplishment, health, loneliness and happiness. The score for overall well-being can also be calculated using

15 items for each of the elements of PERMA and one item measuring happiness. This 16-item version has been used for the current study. Higher scores indicate a higher level of overall well-being or satisfaction in the specific domain. Cronbach's alpha values for the subscales ranged from .79 to .90, indicating good internal consistency.

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985). The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) is a widely used measure of life satisfaction. The scale assesses the cognitive self-evaluations of one's life satisfaction. The SWLS comprises of 5 items scored on a 7-point scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree and the scoring is kept continuous. The results can be interpreted as greater level of satisfaction indicated by higher scores. Reliability for this scale was acceptable, with Cronbach's alpha value being .84.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation and linear regression to examine the relationships among variables and identify significant predictors among the sample. Descriptive statistics summarised the dispersion of scores, correlations assessed the associations and linear regression tested the predictive effects of attitudes towards ageing.

Procedure

The present study aimed to examine the impact of ageing-related attitudes on well-being and life satisfaction among older women. Prior to data collection, all participants were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of confidentiality and anonymity, and informed that their participation in this study was voluntary and they could withdraw at any point. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before the administration of the questionnaires. A total of 50 females between the ages of 65 and 80 years were approached. Data was collected using standardized self-report measures. Ageing-related attitudes were assessed using the Attitudes to Ageing Questionnaire, well-being using the PERMA Profiler, and life satisfaction was assessed using the Satisfaction with Life Scale. Upon completion of data collection, responses were coded for analysis. Descriptive statistics were computed to summarize the sample characteristics and study variables. Pearson's correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships among ageing-related attitudes, well-being, and life satisfaction. Further, linear regression analyses were performed to determine the predictive impact of ageing-related attitudes on well-being and life satisfaction among older women.

Results

Table 1

Mean and SD for Attitudes to Ageing, Well-being and Life Satisfaction (N=50)

	Mean	SD
Psychosocial Loss	18.44	3.38
Physical Change	28.34	3.99
Psychological Growth	32.22	3.39
Life Satisfaction	28.5	3.21
Positive Emotions	8.38	1.34
Engagement	6.47	1.68
Relationships	7.55	1.41
Meaning	8.52	1.27
Accomplishment	8.11	1.37
Total Well-Being	7.98	1.08

Table 1 contains descriptive statistics for attitudes to ageing, well-being and life satisfaction.

Table 2

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis for Attitudes to Ageing, Well-being and Life Satisfaction (N=50)

Variable	P	E	R	M	A	Total WB	LS
PL	-.173	-.124	-.256	-.166	-.193	-.144	-.201
PC	.298*	.295*	.241	.317*	.417**	.288*	.257
PG	.206	-.101	.088	.286*	.294*	.245	.241

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. PL - Psychosocial Loss. PC - Physical Change. PG - Psychological Growth. P - Positive Emotions. E - Engagement. R - Relationships. M - Meaning. A - Accomplishment. Total WB - Total Well-being. LS - Life Satisfaction.

The results of the correlation analyses presented in Table 2 show that the negative attitude of psychosocial loss (PL) was negatively related to all elements of PERMA, the total well-being scores and life satisfaction, which suggests the possibility of inverse relationships among these variables, but these values were not found to be significant. The physical change (PC) subscale of attitudes to ageing was significantly and positively related to positive emotions

(P), engagement (E), meaning (M), accomplishment (A) and overall well-being. This suggests that as scores on physical change increased, scores on these scales also increased. The third subscale of attitudes to ageing, psychological growth (PG) was found to be positively and significantly correlated with meaning (M) and accomplishment (A) subscales of well-being.

Table 3

Regression Analyses for Physical Change and Elements of PERMA Model of Well-being

Model	Unstandardized	Standardized	Standard error	t	p
	Coefficients	Coefficients			
	B	Beta			
(Constant)	5.56		1.32	4.21	<.001
PC (DV: P)	0.10	0.29	0.05	2.16	.036*
(Constant)	2.95		1.66	1.78	.082
PC (DV: E)	0.12	0.28	0.06	2.14	.037*
(Constant)	5.65		1.25	4.52	<.001
PC (DV: M)	0.10	0.32	0.04	2.32	.025*
(Constant)	4.05		1.29	3.14	.003
PC (DV: A)	0.14	0.41	0.05	3.18	.003**

Note. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$ Predictor - Physical Change (PC), Dependent Variables (DV)- Positive Emotion (P), Engagement (E), Meaning (M) and Accomplishment (A).

Regression analyses were conducted to understand the relationships between the variables. It can be noted from Table 3 that ageing related attitude of physical change, which measures one's positive view of physical changes that accompany old age, was found to be a significant predictor of four of the five elements of the PERMA model, namely, positive emotions, engagement, meaning and accomplishment. It is evident from Table 3 that when the value of 'physical change' increases by one unit, the value of 'positive emotion' also increases by 0.10 units. This model also had a low positive relationship between the observed values and the prediction, with physical change explaining 8.86% of the variance (R^2) in the dependent variable of positive emotion. The model for physical change and engagement shows that if the value of 'physical change' changes by one unit, the value of the 'engagement' changes by 0.124 units. Physical change explained 8.71% of the variance (R^2) in engagement. The model for physical change and meaning shows a moderate positive relationship between the observed values and the

prediction. If the value of the 'physical change' changes by one unit, the value of 'meaning' changes by 0.101 units. Physical change explained 10.06% of the variance (R^2) in meaning. The model for physical change and accomplishment shows a moderate positive relationship between the observed values and the prediction and if the value of 'physical change' changes by one unit, the value of 'accomplishment' changes by 0.143 units. Physical change explained 17.4% of the variance (R^2) in accomplishment.

Discussion

This study aims to explore the relationship between attitudes towards ageing among older women and their reported levels of well-being and life satisfaction. Attitudes towards ageing are conceptualised as cognitive and affective evaluations of the ageing process, and have been shown to shape behavioural, emotional and health-related outcomes in later life. In this study, positive attitudes towards ageing, such as positive perceptions of physical changes and

psychological growth, and negative attitudes, such as experiencing psychosocial losses have been examined. Descriptive analyses indicated that participants scored relatively high on positive attitudes towards ageing and comparatively low on negative attitudes, suggesting an overall adaptive orientation towards the ageing process within this sample. With respect to psychological well-being, participants' mean scores exceeded normative values on four of the five dimensions of the PERMA framework, namely, positive emotion, relationship, meaning and accomplishment as well as on overall well-being. This suggests that the participants reported relatively strong functioning across multiple domains of psychological well-being. Furthermore, mean scores for life satisfaction indicated that, on average, participants perceived themselves as satisfied with their lives and current circumstances.

The study hypothesised that positive ageing-related attitudes, specifically perceptions of psychological growth and positive evaluations of physical changes, would be positively associated with both well-being and life satisfaction. The findings partially supported this hypothesis (H1a). Positive attitudes towards ageing demonstrated significant positive associations with overall well-being and four of the five components of the PERMA model except the engagement element. With regard to life satisfaction, although the direction of the relationships between positive ageing attitudes and life satisfaction also suggests a positive trend among the variables, the associations did not reach statistical significance. Therefore, Hypothesis 2a (H2a) was not supported. These results suggest that while adaptive attitudes towards ageing may be more strongly linked to multidimensional psychological well-being, their relationship with global evaluations of life satisfaction may be more complex or influenced by additional moderating variables not examined in this study.

It was hypothesised that psychosocial loss, which reflects a negative ageing-related attitude, would be inversely associated with both well-being and life satisfaction. The findings revealed negative correlations between psychosocial loss and overall well-being, as well as with each of the five components of the PERMA model. Although the direction of these relationships was consistent with theoretical expectations, the associations did not reach statistical significance. Consequently, Hypothesis 1b (H1b) was not supported. Similarly, psychosocial loss shows a negative association with life satisfaction, however, the correlation coefficient was not statistically significant. Therefore, Hypothesis 2b (H2b) was also rejected. These results suggest that, within the present sample, perceptions of psychosocial loss were not sufficiently strong predictors of well-being or life satisfaction to achieve statistical significance, despite the observed directional trends. This may indicate that other protective factors, such as social support, resilience or adaptive coping mechanisms, may have mitigated the potential adverse impact of negative attitudes towards ageing.

Findings indicated a significant association between positive perceptions of physical change and positive emotion, engagement, meaning, accomplishment and overall well-being. Longitudinal studies have shown that individuals who hold more positive views of their own ageing experience better functional health and emotional outcomes over time (Levy et al., 2002; Warmoth et al., 2016). Specifically, positive self-perceptions of ageing have been linked to higher levels of positive affect and lower depressive symptomatology (Bryant et al., 2012; Fernandes-Pires et al., 2024). Research by Westerhof et al. (2014) also indicates that favourable ageing

attitudes are associated with greater overall well-being, even after controlling for objective health status. The significant association with engagement in the present study is also supported by findings suggesting that older adults who interpret physical ageing as manageable rather than debilitating are more likely to maintain participation in social and productive activities (Warmoth et al., 2016). Studies examining subjective ageing and eudaimonic well-being have shown strong link between positive ageing perceptions and greater sense of purpose and mastery (Ugwu & Idemudia, 2025). The association with accomplishment aligns with evidence indicating that older adults who endorse adaptive views of ageing report stronger feelings of competence and continued achievement despite physical changes (Brothers et al., 2016). Hence, the present findings correspond closely with prior empirical work suggesting that positive evaluations of physical change function as psychological resources that support multiple domains of well-being.

On the other hand, psychological growth was significantly associated with meaning and accomplishment, but not with positive emotion, engagement, relationships or life satisfaction. This pattern mirrors findings in the literature distinguishing between hedonic and eudaimonic well-being outcomes. Research indicates that perceiving continued growth in later life is particularly predictive of purpose in life and goal-related fulfilment rather than momentary affective states (Ryff & Singer, 2008). For example, Ryff and Keyes (1995) found that personal growth and purpose in life cluster together as core dimensions of psychological well-being in older adulthood. Similarly, empirical studies show that older adults who endorse growth-oriented ageing attitudes report stronger existential meaning and higher perceived competence (Westerhof et al., 2014). The lack of a significant relationship with life satisfaction has been supported by previous research. Life satisfaction reflects a global cognitive evaluation, which can be influenced by health, socioeconomic status, and social stability (Diener et al., 1985). Research has shown that positive self-perceptions of ageing predict health and functional outcomes, but when contextual factors are taken into account, their relationship with life satisfaction becomes weaker (Westerhof et al., 2014). Thus, the present results contribute to existing literature suggesting that psychological growth in later life may be more closely linked to meaning-oriented and achievement-related elements of well-being than to affective or global evaluative components.

Results of regression analyses show that Physical Change was found to be a major predictor of well-being. Many studies have reported the attitude of physical change to be the most important facet of attitudes to ageing in predicting health and psychological well-being for women (Brown et al., 2015). Studies suggest that having a higher physical resilience can reduce the impact of physical changes that accompany old age (Siltanen et al., 2020). One explanation for positive perception of physical change being important for health and well-being could be that physical changes are one of the first visible signs of ageing and these physical changes can have an impact on many areas of the lives of older adults. Physical changes can limit one's physical activity, based on the strength of the change, consequently reducing the level of autonomy they feel (Parra-Rizo & Sanchis-Soler, 2021). Physical changes can affect the mobility and health of older adults, thereby affecting their general well-being, life satisfaction (Kiełtyka-Słowik et al., 2024) and quality of life (Rejeski & Mihalko, 2001). When one is able to

perceive these changes in a positive light and tries to keep physically fit and active, it can have significant advantages for psychological well-being (Moreno-Agostino et al., 2020). Older females who continue to take part in daily chores and have a relatively active lifestyle may not see physical changes as negative.

In relation to positive emotion, the present findings are consistent with research indicating that adaptive perceptions of physical ageing are associated with higher levels of positive affect and fewer depressive symptoms (Bryant et al., 2012; Westerhof et al., 2014). Longitudinal research has shown that individuals who maintain more positive self-perceptions of ageing experience better emotional regulation and reduced psychological distress over time (Levy et al., 2002). Positive perceptions of physical change may therefore buffer against emotional loss by encouraging adaptive coping mechanisms and decreasing maladaptive rumination regarding bodily changes. With respect to engagement, studies have shown that older adults who have a more favourable view of their physical health are more likely to continue participating actively in social, recreational, and productive activities (Menec, 2003; Warmoth et al., 2016). Engagement, defined as deep involvement in meaningful activities, is strongly influenced by perceived functional ability. Older adults may be more likely to continue participating in valued roles when physical changes are perceived as manageable rather than limiting. The significant link between physical change and meaning has been supported by research that indicates that subjective health assessments are strongly associated with life purpose and existential well-being (Hill & Turiano, 2014). Studies show that individuals who successfully adapt to age-related physical changes are more likely to integrate these experiences into a coherent life narrative, enhancing their sense of purpose and coherence (Westerhof et al., 2014). Positive views of physical change may therefore encourage processes of meaning-making that support more general psychological flourishing. Studies also support the findings regarding the role of positively perceiving physical changes for the accomplishment element. Literature has demonstrated that perceived physical competence and functional ability are associated with higher levels of mastery, self-efficacy, and goal attainment in later life (Rejeski & Mihalko, 2001). Maintaining confidence in their ability to manage physical changes may encourage the older adults to continue to pursue and achieve personally valued goals, reinforcing feelings of competence and achievement. Thus, the present findings align with prior research suggesting that adaptive perceptions of physical ageing function as psychological resources that support multiple dimensions of well-being.

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. The sample consisted exclusively of older females, which limits the generalizability of the findings to older men or mixed-gender populations. Additionally, the sample size was relatively small (N = 50) and drawn from a single geographic area, which may restrict the representativeness of the results. Participants were also generally healthy, which means the findings may not fully capture the experiences of older adults with chronic illnesses or functional limitations. Future research could address these limitations by including larger, more diverse samples that encompass different genders, broader geographic regions, and participants with varying health statuses to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between ageing-related attitudes, well-being, and life satisfaction.

Conclusion

The current study provides evidence for the importance of accepting and embracing change during old age. Studies show the difference between the experiences of individuals having positive and negative attitudes. Levy (2002) contended that while adopting a positive outlook about aging and one's health in later years won't miraculously improve one's health or erase physical changes that are associated with old age, however, fostering optimistic perceptions can significantly impact health and longevity during old age. Levy (2002) reported a difference of 7.5 years in the life expectancy of people having positive and negative attitudes, with individuals with an optimistic outlook living longer than their counterparts. The present study has implications for geriatric counsellors and therapists. The findings can shed light on the issues unique to this population and can help in developing interventions for them. The decade from 2021 to 2030 has been declared as the "Decade of Healthy Ageing" by the World Health Organisation and the United Nations Organisation (2020). Under this Decade of Healthy Ageing, the WHO has called for a change in the general perceptions about ageing and older adults as a major part of 'healthy ageing'. This change in mindset can have benefits for the older adults as well as society at large.

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